

An Analysis of the Effect of Compensation and Job Promotion on Employee Performance Job Satisfaction as a Mediator at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta, Indonesia

Liliani Petrian¹, Rahmat Ingkadijaya², Sofian Lusa³, Myrza Rahmanita⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Trisakti Institute of Tourism

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 22 January 2026	This study aims to analyze the effect of job compensation and job promotion on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediating variable at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta. The approach used is quantitative with an explanatory research design, where data were collected through questionnaires distributed to 140 employees. Data testing was conducted using SEM-PLS analysis to examine the relationship between variables. The results of the study indicate that compensation and job promotion have a significant effect on job satisfaction, which in turn has a significant effect on employee performance. However, the direct effect of compensation on employee performance is not significant, as is the direct effect of job promotion on performance. Furthermore, the results of the indirect effect test indicate that job satisfaction mediates the relationship between compensation and employee performance, as well as between job promotion and employee performance. This study concludes that job satisfaction is an important factor in improving employee performance, and job stability and promotion have a significant impact through mediating job satisfaction.
Corresponding Author: Liliani Petrian	Therefore, companies are advised to focus on improving employee job satisfaction as a strategic effort to improve employee performance and retention.
KEYWORDS: compensation, job promotion, employee performance, job satisfaction	

I. INTRODUCTION

The hospitality industry is a service sector that relies heavily on the quality of interactions between employees and guests. Employee performance is not merely an operational output but also a strategic factor that determines service quality, company image, and long-term business prospects (Asgerirsson et al., 2024). Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta prioritizes guest satisfaction, making it crucial to develop and formulate human resource management strategies, particularly through policies that focus not only on financial aspects but also on professional employee development.

However, workforce dynamics at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta indicate significant retention. HR Department data from 2024 shows a high new employee retention rate (45.2% YTD), followed by a significant resignation rate (23.1% YTD), even reaching 60% in certain periods. This situation illustrates the challenges in retaining a workforce that can potentially incur recurring recruitment and training costs, disrupt operational stability, and risk a decline in consistent service quality.

Theoretically, rewards and promotions are often positioned as key instruments for improving employee motivation, loyalty, and performance (Singhvi et al., 2018). Promotions implemented transparently and based on merit are expected to recognize employee contributions and encourage better performance (Desky, 2023). However, empirical findings at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur indicate that although promotions have been granted to 24% of employees, the policy has not been effective enough to reduce the turnover rate. This fact reinforces the suspicion of a gap between theoretical expectations and actual implementation, for example, regarding the perception of fairness in promotion opportunities and alignment with employee expectations.

In human resource management, job satisfaction is often understood as a psychological mechanism that explains how organizational policies (such as remuneration and promotions) can lead to improved performance (Alsafadi & Altahat, 2021). Employees with higher levels of job satisfaction tend to exhibit stronger work engagement, more stable motivation, and more consistent service behavior in

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the hospitality industry, which directly impacts the quality of the guest experience (Heimerl et al., 2020). Job satisfaction can be considered a mediating variable to explain the relationship between compensation and job promotions on employee performance (Stirpe et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the complexity of HR management is increasing due to the generational diversity within the organization. Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta has an employee composition dominated by Generation Y/Millennials (41.6%), followed by Generation X (39.3%) and Generation Z (19.1%). Differences in values, work preferences, and communication styles between generations have the potential to create a generation gap that can affect perceptions of advancement, promotion opportunities, and ultimately job satisfaction. Therefore, this study is relevant to analyze the effect of compensation and job promotions on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediator, while also considering the context of generational differences as a differentiating aspect that enriches academic contributions and practical empowerment in hotel HR management.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Resource Management

Human Resource Management (HRM) is a fundamental element in organizational success because it focuses on managing people as the primary driver of all company activities (Arokiasamy et al., 2024). Human resources, as employees who are ready, capable, and ready to achieve organizational goals, therefore require a systematic and sustainable managerial approach (Zhang & Villanueva, 2024). HRM is a branch of management science that focuses on managing human roles through training, development, motivation, and other supporting aspects so that organizations can operate effectively and efficiently (Omollo & Juma, 2025). HRM is the process of planning, organizing, directing, and supervising the procurement, development, compensation, integration, maintenance, and termination of employment to achieve organizational, individual, and societal goals in an integrated manner (Green et al., 2006).

Work Compensation

Work compensation encompasses all forms of rewards, both financial and non-financial, provided by an organization to employees in return for their contributions (Hidayat & Djawoto, 2025). Fair and competitive compensation plays a crucial role in increasing employee motivation, loyalty, and performance, encompassing direct and indirect income received by employees for services rendered to the organization (Pudjiarti et al., 2023). Common pay indicators used include salary, bonuses, incentives, allowances, and support facilities, which collectively influence perceptions of fairness and employee well-being (Rachman et al., 2025).

Job Promotion

A job promotion is an organization's recognition of an employee's performance and potential by moving them to a higher position, accompanied by increased authority, responsibility, status, and income (Pane et al., 2025). Promotion, as a move to a higher level in the organizational hierarchy, impacts employee rights and obligations and is seen as a crucial instrument for career development and increased motivation and job satisfaction (Mishra et al., 2025). Factors influencing job promotions include work performance, seniority, competence, loyalty, and organizational needs (Garbha & Abdullahi, 2019). Transparency and fairness in the promotion process are crucial to ensure the policy is trusted as a means of objective career advancement.

Employee Performance

Employee performance describes the work results achieved by an individual or group over a specific period, both in terms of quality and quantity, in accordance with the responsibilities assigned by the organization (Liang & Li, 2025). Performance is defined as the ability to complete tasks optimally with the efficient use of resources (Vuong & Mguyen, 2022). Performance is a key indicator of organizational success because it is directly related to the achievement of company goals and productivity (López-Cabarcos et al., 2022). Common employee performance indicators used include work quality, work quantity, punctuality, efficiency, attendance, teamwork, initiative, and responsibility (Pradhan & Jena, 2016).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a psychological state that reflects an employee's feelings of comfort, security, and satisfaction with their job and work environment (Ratnaningtyas et al., 2025). Job satisfaction arises when employee expectations regarding job aspects, such as peace, promotions, work relationships, and organizational support, are met appropriately (Asgeirsson et al., 2024). Satisfied employees tend to exhibit positive attitudes, high commitment, and constructive work behaviors. There is a reciprocal relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance (Pinheiro & Palma-Moreira, 2025). Good performance can increase satisfaction through recognition and rewards, while high job satisfaction drives motivation and consistent performance (Pudjiastuti & Sijabat, 2022).

III. METODE PENELITIAN

This study uses a quantitative approach with an explanatory research design, because the main focus of the study is to test the causal relationship between work compensation and job promotion on employee performance, with job satisfaction as a mediating variable. The quantitative approach was chosen so that hypothesis testing can be carried out objectively through statistical analysis based on numerical data. The research location is Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta, chosen because it is relevant to the

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context of human resource management which is the focus of the study. The implementation of the research includes the stages of preparing instruments, data collection, data processing, to the range of report preparation during the research period of 2025–2026.

The study population was all employees of Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta. The sampling technique used saturated (census sampling), where all members were filled in as respondents, with the aim of obtaining a comprehensive picture and minimizing sample selection bias. Research data were collected using a questionnaire as the main instrument, which was compiled based on variable indicators from the theoretical basis. The measurement scale used a Likert scale of 1–5 to capture the level of respondent agreement with statements related to compensation, job promotion, job satisfaction, and employee performance, so that the data could be processed quantitatively.

The research variables consist of work compensation (X1) and job promotion (X2) as independent variables, job satisfaction (Z) as mediating variable, and employee performance (Y) as dependent variable. Each variable is operationalized into measurable indicators so that it can be explained empirically through respondents' answers. Data analysis was carried out through descriptive statistics to describe respondents' characteristics and answer tendencies, then continued with SEM-PLS to test the relationship between variables in the research model. SEM-PLS was chosen because it is suitable for testing structural models involving mediation and does not rely strictly on the assumption of data normality. Hypothesis testing was carried out by looking at the t-statistic and p-value values in the SEM-PLS results, with general significance criteria of $t > 1.96$ and $p < 0.05$.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	110	78.6
	Female	30	21.4
	Total	140	100
Generation (Age)	Generation X (1965–1980)	52	37.1
	Generation Y / Millennials (1981–1994)	60	42.9
	Generation Z (1995–2010)	28	20.0
	Total	140	100
Educational Background	Senior High School / Vocational School	64	45.7
	Diploma	35	25.0
	Bachelor’s Degree	37	26.4
	Master’s Degree	4	2.9
Total	140	100	
Marital Status	Single	38	27.1
	Married	102	72.9
Total	140	100	
Length of Employment	1 year	35	25.0
	2 years	30	21.4
	3 years	23	16.4
	> 3 years	52	37.1
	Total	140	100
Position	Staff	91	65.0
	Supervisor	19	13.6
	Manager	19	13.6
	Head of Department (HOD)	11	7.9
Total	140	100	
Department	A & G	3	2.1
	Engineering	12	8.6
	FB Product	28	20.0
	FB Service	16	11.4

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Characteristics	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
	Finance & Accounting	13	9.3
	Front Office	18	12.9
	Housekeeping	24	17.1
	Human Resources	8	5.7
	IT	1	0.7
	Sales & Marketing	17	12.1
Total		140	100

Source: Data diolah (2025)

Based on the respondent characteristics table (N = 140), the majority of respondents were male (110 people; 78.6%) compared to female (30 people; 21.4%). In terms of generation, respondents were dominated by Generation Y/Millennials (60 people; 42.9%), followed by Generation X (52 people; 37.1%) and Generation Z (28 people; 20.0%). Educational background showed the largest proportion in High School/Vocational High School (64 people; 45.7%), followed by Bachelor's (37 people; 26.4%), Diploma (35 people; 25.0%) and Master's (4 people; 2.9%). From marital status, most respondents were married (102 people; 72.9%) while unmarried (38 people; 27.1%).

Based on length of service, the most respondents were in the category of >3 years (52 people; 37.1%), then 1 year (35 people; 25.0%), 2 years (30 people; 21.4%) and 3 years (23 people; 16.4%). In terms of position, the majority were staff (91 people; 65.0%), while supervisors and managers were 19 people (13.6%) and HOD 11 people (7.9%). In terms of departments, the most respondents came from FB Product (28 people; 20.0%) and Housekeeping (24 people; 17.1%), followed by Front Office (18 people; 12.9%) and Sales & Marketing (17 people; 12.1%), while the departments with the fewest respondents were IT (1 person; 0.7%) and A&G (3 people; 2.1%).

Table 2. Validity Test

Variable	Quisioner Item	Loading Factor	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Description
Compensation	X1.1	0.778	0.635	Valid
	X1.2	0.833		Valid
	X1.3	0.818		Valid
	X1.4	0.729		Valid
	X1.5	0.757		Valid
Job promotion	X2.1	0.738	0.718	Valid
	X2.2	0.857		Valid
	X2.3	0.876		Valid
	X2.4	0.782		Valid
	X2.5	0.868		Valid
	X2.6	0.826		Valid
	X2.7	0.893		Valid
	X2.8	0.894		Valid
	X2.9	0.879		Valid
Employee performance	Y1	0.803	0.708	Valid
	Y2	0.812		Valid
	Y3	0.891		Valid
	Y4	0.845		Valid
	Y5	0.861		Valid
	Y6	0.870		Valid
	Y7	0.779		Valid
	Y8	0.873		Valid
Job satisfaction	Z1	0.854	0.644	Valid
	Z2	0.785		Valid
	Z3	0.820		Valid
	Z4	0.836		Valid
	Z5	0.708		Valid

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS (2025)

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Based on the results of the convergent validity test, all questionnaire items were declared valid because they met the outer loading criteria ≥ 0.700 , so that each indicator was able to adequately represent the measured construct. In addition, construct validity was also supported by the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values which were all above the required threshold (generally > 0.50), namely Compensation = 0.635, Job Promotion = 0.718, Employee Performance = 0.708, and Job Satisfaction = 0.644, which indicated that each construct was able to explain the proportion of indicator variance strongly and adequately.

Tabel 3. Uji Reliabilitas

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Description
Compensation	0.809	0.874	Reliable
Job promotion	0.950	0.958	Reliable
Employee performance	0.941	0.951	Reliable
Job satisfaction	0.861	0.900	Reliable

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS (2025)

The results of the reliability test show that all constructs in this study have good internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha and Composite Reliability values of more than 0.70

Tabel 5. Direct Effect

Variable Relationships	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Description
Job satisfaction -> Employee performance	0.677	0.688	0.124	5.440	0	Significant
Compensation -> Job satisfaction	0.202	0.223	0.09	2.245	0.025	Significant
Compensation -> Employee performance	0.011	0.022	0.099	0.116	0.908	No Significant
Job promotion -> Job satisfaction	0.71	0.694	0.081	8.713	0	Significant
Job promotion -> Employee performance	-0.06	-0.07	0.139	0.431	0.667	No Significant

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS (2025)

Table 5 shows the results of the direct influence between the variables in the research model. The effect of job satisfaction on employee performance is very significant with a T-statistic value of 5.440 (p-value = 0.000), which means that job satisfaction makes a significant contribution to employee performance. In addition, the effect of compensation on job satisfaction is also significant with a T-statistic value of 2.245 (p-value = 0.025), indicating that compensation has a positive impact on job satisfaction.

Tabel 6. Indirect Effect

Variable Relationships	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Signifikansi
Compensation -> Job satisfaction -> Employee performance	0.137	0.153	0.068	2.016	0.044	Significant
Job promotion -> Job satisfaction -> Employee performance	0.481	0.478	0.106	4.533	0	Significant

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS (2025)

each, which meet the reliability criteria. Compensation has Cronbach's alpha = 0.845 and Composite Reliability = 0.894, job promotion has Cronbach's alpha = 0.912 and Composite Reliability = 0.946, Employee performance has Cronbach's alpha = 0.898 and Composite Reliability = 0.934, and job satisfaction has Cronbach's alpha = 0.863 and Composite Reliability = 0.912.

Table 4. R-Square (R²)

Variable	R ²
Employee performance	0.404
Job satisfaction	0.708

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS (2025)

The R² value for Employee Performance (Y) of 0.404 indicates that 40.4% of the variation in employee performance can be explained by the influence of work improvement and job promotion. This indicates that this model has a moderate level of explanation for the performance variable. Meanwhile, the R² value for Job Satisfaction (Z) of 0.708 indicates that 70.8% of the variation in job satisfaction can be explained by work compensation and job promotion, which also indicates that this model has a moderate explanation for job satisfaction.

Conversely, the direct influence on employee performance is not significant, with a T-statistic of only 0.116 (p-value = 0.908). For job promotion, its effect on job satisfaction is very significant, with a T-statistic of 8.713 (p-value = 0.000), but its effect on employee performance is not significant, with a T-statistic of 0.431 (p-value = 0.667). Thus, only a few relationships show a significant influence, especially those concerning job satisfaction..

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Table 6 shows the results of the indirect effect, which measures the indirect influence between variables in the research model. Compensation through job satisfaction has a significant indirect effect on employee performance, with a T-statistic of 2.016 (p -value = 0.044), indicating that job satisfaction mediates the relationship between compensation and employee performance. Similarly, job promotion through job satisfaction has a highly significant indirect effect on employee performance, with a T-statistic of 4.533 (p -value = 0.000), indicating that job satisfaction also mediates the relationship between job promotion and employee performance. These two relationships proved significant, indicating the importance of job satisfaction as a mediator in the influence of recovery and job promotion on employee performance.

Job satisfaction at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta, Indonesia, significantly impacts employee performance. Satisfied employees tend to be more motivated, have a higher level of commitment, and demonstrate greater engagement in their tasks, which in turn improves performance. When employees feel valued and satisfied with aspects of their jobs, they are more productive and produce higher-quality work.

Compensation at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta, Indonesia, significantly impacts job satisfaction. Fair and competitive compensation in the form of salary, benefits, and other benefits makes employees feel valued, which increases their satisfaction with the organization. Compensation that aligns with employee expectations can create a more positive work environment and motivate them to contribute more effectively.

Furthermore, job promotions at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta, Indonesia, significantly impact job satisfaction because they provide employees with opportunities for growth, recognition for their achievements, and increased status and income. Promotions are perceived as a reward for their hard work and dedication, which increases their sense of satisfaction and loyalty to the organization.

Compensation at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta, Indonesia, did not significantly impact employee performance in this study. This is likely because, while employee compensation does influence job satisfaction, its direct impact on performance may be limited by other factors that influence intrinsic motivation. Employees may be satisfied with their compensation, but without other factors such as job challenges, managerial support, or career development, they may not feel sufficiently motivated to improve their performance. Optimal performance is often influenced by more complex psychological and work environment factors, such as job satisfaction, relationships with coworkers, and development opportunities.

Similarly, job promotions at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta, Indonesia, did not significantly impact

employee performance in this study. This may be because job promotions provide recognition and opportunities for employee development. Not all employees may be ready or motivated to take on the increased responsibilities that come with a promotion. Other factors, such as employee readiness for new responsibilities or the quality of training and development support provided by the organization, may play a larger role in determining whether job promotions actually improve performance.

Employee performance at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta, Indonesia, is not always directly influenced by higher status or position, but rather by how motivated employees feel, have opportunities for development, and are accepted in their new roles.

Compensation at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta, Indonesia, influences employee performance through job satisfaction, as fair promotions and the ability to feel appreciated boost employee motivation and commitment. This job satisfaction ultimately leads to improved performance, as satisfied employees tend to be more productive, loyal, and enthusiastic about achieving company goals. Conversely, inadequate compensation can decrease job satisfaction, ultimately negatively impacting employee performance and motivation.

Promotions at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta, Indonesia, increase job satisfaction by providing recognition and growth opportunities, which boost employee motivation and commitment. This satisfaction ultimately leads to improved performance, as employees are more motivated to perform better.

Several previous studies have shown a significant relationship between the variables studied. Job satisfaction has been shown to significantly influence employee performance, as explained in the studies of Gazi et al. (2020) and Srivastav et al. (2024), who found that the level of job satisfaction directly influences employee work behavior and performance. Furthermore, compensation has a significant effect on job satisfaction, as revealed in the studies of Ardianto et al. (2024) and Mabaso & Dlamini (2017), who confirmed that fair and competitive independence plays an important role in increasing job satisfaction. Finally, job promotions have also been shown to significantly influence job satisfaction, as demonstrated by studies by Mahardiansyah & Mauludin (2025) and Mustapha & Zakaria (2013), who found that fair and transparent promotion opportunities increase employee job satisfaction.

Idris et al. (2021) found that job satisfaction mediates the relationship between compensation and employee performance, so that an effective compensation package increases job satisfaction, which in turn has a positive and significant impact on employee performance. Job promotion influences employee performance through job satisfaction, as Berber et al. (2022) found that job promotion increases job satisfaction levels, and job satisfaction subsequently

contributes positively to employee performance, so job satisfaction acts as a significant mediator between job promotion and performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study shows that job advancement and job promotions significantly influence employee job satisfaction, which in turn influences employee performance at Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta. Although the direct effect of compensation and promotions on employee performance is insignificant, both have a strong impact through the mediation of job satisfaction. Therefore, maintaining job satisfaction is key to improving employee performance in the hospitality industry.

This study makes an important contribution to the development of human resource management theory, particularly in the hospitality industry. By demonstrating the role of job satisfaction as a mediator between compensation, job promotions, and employee performance, this study enriches understanding of the factors influencing employee performance in the hospitality sector and provides new insights for more in-depth HRM studies.

The implication of this research is the importance of Artotel Suites Mangkuluhur Jakarta's management focusing on maintaining employee job satisfaction, by paying attention to job renewal and promotion aspects. Transparent and fair policies in both aspects can increase employee motivation and loyalty, which will ultimately contribute to improved performance and guest satisfaction.

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